

ROOM TEMPERATURE CURE MONITORING USING A DMA/THERMAL FLUX CELL AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF A PHENOLIC SYNTACTIC FOAM

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ABSTRACT

For an optimization of the manufacture of phenolic syntactic foam, the transformation process of a phenolic resin was studied. In this work, the effect of the catalyst rate, the glass microsphere content and the working conditions (volume, room cure temperature) on reactivity of phenolic resin was investigated by a novel technique developed by METRAVIB: a coupled calorimetry-DMA analysis. It allows simultaneous characterization of resin cure, as well as of rheological changes that take place during polymerization at room temperature. The information obtained can then be processed in order to provide accurate data on gelation time and cure kinetic behavior. Chemorheological models can then be created to predict the physical behavior of the resin leading to the optimization of the industrial composites part manufacturing. After curing, viscoelastic properties of phenolic matrix and syntactic foam were studied using a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA) in tension/compression mode. The storage modulus and the damping factor were measured over a wide temperature range and related to the microstructural parameters of syntactic foams. In particular, two phenomena were highlighted: the post-curing and the loss of volatiles, also demonstrated by DSC. Then, a better understanding of the damage mechanisms of these materials would be useful in determining actual material limits, improving phenomenological modeling and developing novel formulations (fibers, coated microspheres) in the future. To achieve this goal, an experimental study of the compression behavior was performed by a macroscopic test and by the mean of synchrotron X-ray tomography. High spatial resolution and in-situ scanning in stepwise mode allowed unique qualitative and quantitative analysis of the composite microstructure during compression testing. This technique was shown to be a powerful tool to examine the evolution of damage during in-situ mechanical test with fraction and morphology of broken spheres and damage spatial distribution in order to determine local deformation mechanisms.

1 INTRODUCTION

Syntactic foams are composites containing hollow microspheres dispersed in a polymeric resin. These materials are multi-functional due to their attractive mechanical properties coupled with good thermal insulating and light-weight properties. These advantages make syntactic foams a popular choice for core material in sandwich structured composites. The hollow spheres may be made up of glass, metals, polymers or ceramics. Syntactic foams are essentially isotropic materials due to the randomness of the microstructure. Otherwise, there is an increased awareness for the need to improve fire standards in these areas where public safety is important. An approach to improving the fire

performance of these composites is through the use of resins that are less susceptible to heat and flame. In this way, the use of phenolic syntactic foams seems to be a better compromise of mechanical strength, isolation and fire behaviour. The phenolic resins are a class of compounds that have superior fire and flammability properties compared to other thermoset resins such as the polyesters and epoxies. Because of their unique chemical structure which primarily comprises C-C bonds in aromatic rings [1], phenolic resins have intrinsic resistance to ignition, low generation of smoke and relatively low cost. When phenolic resin based structures do burn, a high amount of porous carbon char is rapidly formed, as an effect of the thermal degradation reaction, which insulates and protects underlying material. Low density and highly porous chars tend to provide the best thermal insulation. The char layer reduces the conduction of heat to the underlying virgin material and thereby slows the decomposition reaction of the polymer matrix. An additional valuable property derived from the phenolic resin is the ability to retain its physical properties at high temperatures. Due to their fire properties, it might appear reasonable to expect phenolic syntactic foam to show good structural performance in fire.

Curing of the matrix resin is a determining step in manufacturing thermoset composites because of its significant influence on the quality of the product. Besides, for our industrial context, two requirements for manufacturing process were imposed. First, the curing had to be at room cure temperature. And, the gel time had to be greater than or equal to 1 hour. Indeed, a sufficient time was needed during which the resin was still handled after mixing (before rubbery state). Therefore, a clear understanding of the curing mechanisms and the ability to develop suitable kinetic models to simulate cure processes are essential to predict and control the quality and the performances of phenolic syntactic foam.

Resole phenolic resins are produced by a condensation reaction between phenol and formaldehyde. These resins are formed by reacting phenol with an excess of formaldehyde (molar ratio P/F > 1) under alkaline conditions. The mechanisms of the reactions leading to the formation of resole phenolic resins have been the object of a number of studies. The formation of hydroxymethylphenols, the condensation reactions of hydroxymethylphenols to form resole precursors involving the loss of water, and the effect of pH and temperature on these reactions have received considerable attention. The chemistry is difficult to study as the result of the intractable nature of the cured resin. However, the evidence suggests that methylene linkages predominate) although the cured resin may have a number of different crosslinks. The polymerization and the formation of a cross-linked network involve the use of heat and/ or a catalyst. In this work, acid catalysts were used for curing at room temperature.

Unlike thermoplastic polymers the processing of thermosets includes the chemical reactions of cure. The cure begins by the growth and branching of chains. As the reaction proceeds, the increase in molecular weight accelerates, causing an increase in viscosity, and reduction in the total number of molecules. Eventually several chains become linked together into a network of infinite molecular weight. The abrupt and irreversible transformation from a viscous liquid to an elastic gel or rubber is called the gel point. The gel point of a chemically cross-linking system can be defined as the instant at which the weight average molecular weight diverges to infinity.

Gelation is the incipient formation of a cross-linked network, and it is the most distinguishing characteristic of a thermoset. A thermoset loses its ability to flow and is no longer processable above the gel point, and therefore gelation defines the upper limit of the work life. Gelation may be detected as the point at which the reacting resin just becomes insoluble, or as the point where the mechanical loss tangent $\tan \delta$ becomes frequency independent or the onset of the increase in the stiffness in a dynamic rheology measurement. Gelation does not usually inhibit cure (e.g., the reaction rate remains unchanged), and it cannot be detected by techniques sensitive only to the chemical reaction, such as differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Beyond the gel point, reaction proceeds toward the formation of one infinite network with substantial increases in crosslink density, glass transition temperature and ultimate physical properties [2].

Vitrification, a completely distinct phenomenon from gelation, may or may not occur during cure depending on the cure temperature relative to the T_g for full cure. Vitrification is glass formation due to T_g increasing from below T_{cure} to above T_{cure} as a result of the cure reaction, and is defined as the point where $T_g = T_{cure}$. Vitrification can occur at any stage during the reaction to form either an ungelled glass or a gelled glass. It can be avoided by curing at or above $T_{g\infty}$, the glass transition

temperature for the fully cured network. In the glassy state, the rate of reaction will usually undergo a significant decrease and fall below the chemical reaction rate as the reaction becomes controlled by the diffusion of reactants. Unlike gelation, vitrification is reversible by heating, and chemical control of cure may be re-established by heating to devitrify the partially cured thermoset. Vitrification may be detected by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) as a frequency-dependent transition resulting in a glassy modulus typically >1 GPa. The shift from chemical control to diffusion control of the reaction may be observed by a decay of the reaction rate, which is often observed when T_g reaches 10 – 15°C above T_{cure} [2].

In this study, a novel technique is presented which allows simultaneous characterization of resin cure, as well as rheological changes that take place during polymerization. These characterizations were performed with an innovative thermal flux cell combined with a Dynamical Mechanical Analyzer (DMA) apparatus. Changes in temperature and thermal fluxes were directly monitored as well as the stiffness variations of the sample during processing. The experimental data were processed in order to provide accurate data on gel time, vitrification phenomenon and cure kinetics. For this work, the cure monitoring of phenolic resole resin was studied on two states: neat state and filler-resin blends. The influence of parameters as the catalyst rate, the working conditions (volume, room cure temperature) and the glass microsphere content were analyzed on the reactivity of phenolic resole resin. In particular, the formation of network structures is a complex process not only with respect to the chemical reactions leading to the formation of the spatial structure, but also with respect to the physical phenomena accompanying it (structure-formation, transition of the system from the liquid to the solid state). The introduction of filler into such systems may be a method of actively intervening in either one or other of these processes. Without adequate experimental material (in the absence of formulating theoretical ideas), it is difficult to predict which process will be affected since it is a consequence of an entire range of factors: the mechanisms of the chemical reaction; the surface properties of the filler; structure-formation processes; reactions between reagents and the filler, between the polymer and the filler, etc [3].

After the characterization of the curing progression, the cure state was evaluated by two complementary techniques, Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA). The values of heat flow for the first technique reflect the actual chemical state and the mechanical values for the second one reflect the actual physical state. By these means, the degree of cure could be calculated.

Generally, syntactic foams possess very good specific properties, especially compressive characteristics, due to the tailor ability of their microstructures. Hence, it was important to understand the failure characteristic of syntactic foams during compressive deformation for future improvement of formulations (fibers, coated microspheres). To achieve this, a compression study based on both a macroscopic test and in-situ X-ray tomography was performed. The latter is a nondestructive technique shown to be a very powerful tool to characterize the microstructure of cellular materials during in situ mechanical tests. It was employed to examine the evolution of damage during in stepwise uniaxial compression testing with fraction and morphology of broken spheres and damage spatial distribution in order to determine local deformation mechanisms [4].

2 MATERIAL AND TEST PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials and fabrication methods

Specimens for this research were produced by mechanical dispersion of glass hollow microspheres S38 from 3M Company, in resole phenolic resins. They were processed by varying the volume fraction of microspheres: 0% (Matrix, MAT) and 45% (Syntactic foam, SF). The phenolic based systems were cured at room temperature through the careful addition of two acid catalysts, *p*-toluene sulfonic acid PTSA and partial phosphate ester which is also for the latter a flame retardant additive.

2.2 In-situ cure monitoring with DMA/Thermal flux cell

The thermal cell possesses two heat flux sensors located on both sides of the sample. The heat flux and temperature are monitored by these flux sensors. The sample shrinkage and stiffness are respectively measured by the static displacement and the dynamic response of the DMA.

The thermal and dynamic mechanical measurements were carried out with the new thermal cell HFC200 installed on a METRAVIB DMA+450 (see Figure 1). The heat flux cell consists of two upper and lower plates with a cavity of 5 mL between them to hold the sample. This novel heat flux cell enables direct injection of the liquid resin into a closed mold. The temperature control is ensured by the thermal enclosure of the DMA instrument. The resin is contained in the mold where the upper and lower surfaces act as heat flux sensors. A Teflon ring covers the two plates to provide insulation of the sample to its surrounding to minimize side thermal effects. The heat flux and temperature signals are directly monitored by the area heat flux sensors, which deliver electrical signal proportional to heat flux density (W/m^2) passing through them. The heat flux cell is calibrated with a calibrated electric heater. The stiffness K and $\tan \delta$ result are from the dynamic displacement and the force of the DMA instrument. The dynamic solicitation is processed to a voltage generator and a power amplifier, then the signal is transmitted to an electrodynamic exciter (magnetic circuit and exciting coils). The signal is analysed by a dynamic displacement sensor and piezoelectric force sensor. Mechanical properties can then be derived from the stiffness response, which is the raw measured signal of the DMA. A thin layer of demolding agent is sprayed on the sample holders for the removal of the cured resin.

Figure 1: Thermal flux cell HFC200 on DMA+450: (a) design of the fixture and (b) working principle.

For this work, due to the industrial specification that indicates a curing at room temperature, the thermal chamber was not used. The test was carried out on phenolic resole resin with and without hollow glass microspheres (45% v/v S38 from 3M) at 1 μm amplitude. The study of the different parameters is summarized in the following Table 1:

Systems	Phenolic resole resin (neat)	Phenolic resole syntactic foam
<i>Parameters</i>		
1	Catalyst rate	Hollow glass microspheres
2	Volume of the blend	Catalyst rate
3	Room temperature	

Table 1: Summary of the various parameters studied on the influence of the reactivity of the phenolic resole resin at room temperature.

For volumes greater than 5 mL, the cell remained suitable for larger containers but the measurement of the thermal flux was only performed by the upper specimen holder.

2.3 Characterization of the cure state of phenolic resole system

Differential Scanning Calorimetry and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis are two powerful complementary techniques for evaluating the state of the cure of thermoset resins.

The technique DSC, a METTLER TOLEDO DSC 1 STARe System, was used to measure the residual heat of cure remaining in a sample of phenolic resins with and without hollow glass microspheres from -50°C to 450°C at 10°C/min in inert atmosphere.

DMA test is widely used to investigate the structures and the viscoelastic behaviour of polymeric and composite materials for determining relative stiffness and damping characteristics. The dynamic mechanical measurements were conducted on METRAVIB DMA50. The cured specimens were tested in tension/compression mode at multi-frequency from 0.01-30 Hz and 5 μm amplitude from 0°C to 200°C at 1°C/min. The specimen sizes were 12.5 mm long x 5 mm wide and 4 mm thick. The viscoelastic parameter such as the storage modulus E' and the damping factor $\tan \delta$ were plotted with temperature. These values change with temperature and different relaxations could be seen especially the relaxation α associated with glass transition.

2.3 Compression testing

Macroscopic test

Uniaxial compressive tests were performed for the evaluation and the comparison of the compressive strength of the phenolic matrix and the phenolic syntactic foam. Cylindrical specimens of diameter 30 mm and of height 60 mm were compressed between two stainless steel platens and load was applied with a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. An Instron machine equipped with a non-contacting video extensometer for strain measurement was used. Then, the failed test specimens were examined by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) to record the fractographic features.

Compression tests by in-situ X-ray tomography

Internal observation of damage during the compression tests was also carried out by means of a three-dimensional (3D) non-destructive technique, high-resolution X-ray tomography (see Figure 2), only for phenolic syntactic foam. Using this technique, disturbance-free information about the microstructure throughout the volume can be obtained. Tomography combines information from a large number of X-ray radiographs taken with different viewing angles of the sample. The technique contains a computed step, i.e., it includes a recalculation step during which a 3D map of the local absorption coefficients in each elementary volume of the sample is retrieved from the set of absorption radiographs. This map gives an indirect image of the microstructure. In the present study, the samples were scanned using a high-resolution X-ray tomography located at the ESRF (European Synchrotron Research Facility, BM05 beamline) in Grenoble (France). X-ray tomography was performed at a voxel size of $(0.625 \mu\text{m})^3$. The energy was set to 60 keV. A set of 3500 projections was taken within 360°. The detector was a CCD camera with 2048 x 2048 sensitive elements coupled with an X-ray-sensitive laser screen. The force and the crosshead displacement were recorded on a computer and monitored during the test. A first scan was recorded in order to characterize the initial state. The sample was then loaded step by step in compression. At each step of measurement, the sample is scanned. From the pictures collected, the ESRF software reconstructs slice by slice the volume of the specimen. These slices are then visually analyzed to evaluate the damage kinetics. The size of the sample was determined as a function of the resolution needed. Here a parallelepiped of 5 mm side was loaded.

Figure 2: Loading set up for microtomography examination: (a) Photo and (b) Diagram.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 In-situ cure monitoring with DMA/Thermal flux cell of phenolic resole resin based materials

For a formulation (50 mL) without filler, with 3% A + 2% B w/w catalysts, the Figure 3 shows K , $\tan \delta$, the sample temperature and the heat flux measured by coupled calorimetry-DMA analysis at 5, 10 and 20 Hz at room cure temperature ($T_{\text{cure}}=24.8^{\circ}\text{C}$). The gelation phenomenon can be demonstrated by different ways. First, a sudden strong increase in stiffness was observed after a latency time. The onset of increase in stiffness was interpreted as gelation. It was also detected as the point at which $\tan \delta$ becomes independent on the frequency. It corresponds in the $\tan \delta$ curves to the onset of the $\tan \delta$ decrease. The gelation process results in an equilibrium elastic modulus. It appeared at approximately 28 min. After the critical point i.e. liquid-to-rubber-transition, the material began to develop a significant modulus. Then, the second $\tan \delta$ peak, which is frequency-dependent, is a typical indication that the actual glass transition temperature reaches the curing temperature and causes vitrification. It is associated with the transition from a rubbery modulus to a glassy modulus. At this condition, the mobility of the reacting groups was hindered and restricted with the reduction of free volume. This thereby led to an extremely slow reaction, with the reaction rate now controlled by diffusion rather than being controlled by chemical factors.

These mechanical phenomena can be correlated to the thermal phenomena through sensitive measurements provided by the device HFC200. First, changes in sample temperature and thermal flux indicate an exothermic reaction because of their increase directly after mixing. But their evolutions are linked to gelation phenomenon. Indeed, the thermal reactivity between before and after gelation was not the same, a sudden increase of the temperature or the heat flux was observed when the stiffness increased suddenly. Then, when the final modulus was obtained, these two thermal parameters decreased.

Influence of catalyst rate

In order to study the influence of catalyst rate on reactivity of phenolic resole resin, four catalyst rates were examined for a volume of 50 mL at $f=10$ Hz and $T_{\text{cure}}=25.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. As can be seen from stiffness curves in Figure 4, gelation time decreased with the increase of catalyst rate. It was also correlated with the sample temperature reached during the crosslinking.

Figure 3: Evolution of (a) K and Tan δ , (b) sample temperature and (c) heat flux during cure of phenolic resin by coupled calorimetry-DMA analysis ($T_{cure} = 24.8^{\circ}\text{C}$; 50 mL).

Figure 4: Evolution of (a) K, (b) sample temperature and (c) heat flux during cure of phenolic resin by varying the catalyst rate by coupled calorimetry-DMA analysis ($T_{cure} = 25.5^{\circ}\text{C}$, $f = 10$ Hz, 50 mL).

Influence of volume of the mixture

Also, so as to analyse the effect of volume of the mixture on reactivity of phenolic resole resin, three volumes (5, 25 and 50 mL) of the mixture were examined and their respective results are listed in

Table 2, with 3% A + 2% B w/w catalysts. As shown in this Table, gelation time decreased with the increase of volume of the blend due to an increase in sample temperature with the volume (exothermic process).

Volume of the blend (mL)	Gel time (min)	Vitrification time (min) (average peak in $\tan \delta$)	Peak exothermic temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Maximum heat flux (W)
5	>> 120	>> 120	22.48	0.00
25	26.47	49.02	44.48	0.63
50	19.69	/	68.42	4.58

Table 2: Gelation and vitrification times, peak exothermic temperature and maximum heat flux for different volume of the blend at room cure temperature ($T_{\text{cure}}=26^{\circ}\text{C}$, $f=10$ Hz).

Influence of the variation of room cure temperature

Also, so as to analyse the effect of the variation of room temperature during industrial process on reactivity of phenolic resole resin, three temperatures (23.9, 25.3 and 29.3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) were examined for a volume of 50 mL with 3% A + 2% B w/w catalysts. As can be seen from stiffness curves in Figure 5, gelation time decreased with the increase of the outside temperature. The correlation between the heat flux/sample temperature and reaction kinetic shows that condensation cure reaction of phenolic resole resin is clearly a thermos-activated process.

Figure 5: Evolution of K and (a) sample temperature, (b) heat flux during cure of phenolic resole resin by varying the room cure temperature by coupled calorimetry-DMA analysis ($f=10$ Hz, 50 mL).

Influence of the presence of hollow glass microspheres

Also, so as to analyse the effect of filler on reactivity of phenolic resole resin, the two following systems were compared: the resin with a system in which 45% v/v hollow glass microspheres S38 (3MTM) were introduced and the neat matrix with 6% A + 4% B w/w catalysts and for a volume of 50 mL in the two cases. As it can be seen in Figure 6, the reaction with glass beads seems to be completely blocked. Indeed, no thermal flux was observed and there was no variation of stiffness. Incorporation of filler into phenolic resole resin at high concentration significantly affected the cure kinetics of the network formation. Their inhibiting effect may be due by different causes: sterical hindrance caused by the sorption of the reacting monomers on the surface of fillers (physisorption), basic pH of fillers (9.5 according the company 3M) which would slow down the role of catalysts, reduced volume of resin involved in the mixture. They could also interfere with functional groups of the reacting monomers (hydrogen-bonds). As a consequence, the final network of the phenolic resole resin in presence of fillers was not built as quickly as and homogenously and tightly as that of the pure resin. Another inhibiting influence could be also that the hollow glass microspheres may absorb heat and act as a heat sink in the composites. Heat diffusion within the mixture was slowed down by fillers. Then, for the rest of the study, higher catalyst rates were used. For a system of syntactic foam (50 mL), with 9% A + 6% B w/w catalysts, the Figure 7 shows stiffness K and $\tan \delta$ measured by coupled calorimetry-DMA analysis at 10 Hz and at room cure temperature. As for neat phenolic resin, two peaks were found in the $\tan \delta$ curves. The first peak was defined as gelation point (onset of increase in stiffness) and the second as vitrification.

Figure 6: Evolution of (a) stiffness, (b) sample temperature and (c) heat flux during cure at room temperature of phenolic resole resin with and without hollow glass microspheres by coupled calorimetry-DMA analysis for the same catalyst rate 6% A + 4% B w/w ($T_{cure}=25^{\circ}C$, 50 mL).

Figure 7: Evolution of stiffness and $Tan \delta$ during cure at room temperature of phenolic resole syntactic foam by coupled calorimetry-DMA analysis ($T_{cure}=25.9$, $f= 10$ Hz, 50 mL).

Influence of catalyst rate for phenolic resole syntactic foam

In order to study the influence of catalyst rate on reactivity of phenolic resole syntactic foam, four catalyst rates were examined and their respective results are listed in Table 3, for a volume of 50 mL. As can be seen from stiffness curves in this Table, gelation time decreased with the increase of catalyst rate. It was also correlated with the sample temperature reached during the crosslinking.

Catalyst rate	Gel time (min)	Vitrification time (min) (average peak in $\tan \delta$)	Peak exothermic temperature ($^{\circ}C$)	Maximum heat flux (W)
x 8 : 6 % A – 4 % B	320.1	1,560.3	29.01	0.21
x 11.2 : 8 % A – 6 % B	67.8	520.8	31.42	0.30
x 12 : 9 % A – 6 % B	18	54.6	44.53	1.58
x 16 : 12 % A – 8 % B	18.97	27.0	48.85	3.62

Table 3: Gelation and vitrification times, peak exothermic temperature and maximum heat flux for different catalyst rates at room cure temperature ($T_{cure}=25.5^{\circ}C$, $f= 10$ Hz, 50mL).

3.2 Study the cure state after processing

Cured phenolic resins with and without hollow glass microspheres were analyzed by DSC (see Figure 8a). The catalyst rate used for matrix is 2 % w/w A + 1 % w/w B and 7 % w/w A + 5 % w/w B for syntactic foam. Two phenomena were observed from about 40 to 250°C: a large endotherm, superimposed with an exotherm. The endotherm was related to a considerable vaporization of water and loss of other volatiles as residual formaldehyde and the catalyst PTSA. Indeed, water is also by-product of the condensation cure reaction and is initially present as a solvent in the resin. The large exotherm occurring at the same time with the release of water endotherm was linked to the residual polymerisation. So, it was very difficult to evaluate the degree of cure and to establish kinetic models. The plots of the storage modulus E' and the damping factor $\tan \delta$, versus temperature by DMA test for the cured phenolic resole matrix (0.75% w/w A + 0.5% w/w B, 50 mL) are shown in Figure 8b. The magnitude of E' began to decrease from about 60°C, which is related to a primary relaxation T_g associated to the glass transition. However, this variation was not complete since from 89°C the storage modulus increased slightly whatever the frequency. The transition from glass state into the rubbery state seems to be stopped. Indeed, in the $\tan \delta$ curves, usually, the T_g is shown as a peak and to be frequency dependent confirming it as a relaxation event. For this phenolic system, on the contrary, the peak shows no frequency dependence because of the appearance of two phenomena. Once the material was heated through this transition, the post-curing and the loss of volatiles (water, formaldehyde) occurred which led to the stabilization and the increase of the storage modulus. Upon post-curing, phenolic materials continued to crosslink due to the presence of active sites available even after they were cured at room temperature. Thus, the decrease in the storage modulus in the transition region associated with glass transition was shifted to a higher temperature. These analyses confirm also a non-complete cure of phenolic resole resin because of the room cure temperature. These results were consistent with DSC analyses. When vitrification happened, the sample temperature was not enough high to allow the polymerization to continue. The system was fixed, the crosslinking rate was extremely slow and a heating above the glass transition temperature was required to obtain a state close to a fully cured material.

Figure 8: The thermal behaviour for cured samples by (a) DSC test on phenolic matrix and phenolic syntactic foam at a heating rate of 10°C/min describing (b) DMA test with Storage modulus E' and $\tan \delta$ response at a heating rate of 1°C/min for the phenolic resole matrix.

3.2 Compression testing

Macroscopic test

Figure 9a is a sample plot of the compressive stress-strain curve for the syntactic foam material under study. Three different regions can be identified. The first region was characterized by a linear-elastic behavior of the syntactic foam. The region ended when the material started to yield and reaches its compressive yield strength. Upon yielding, the microspheres became crushed under the compression load and severe damage occurred. Yielding and inelastic damage occurred during the test as the sides of the specimen barrel outward under compression loading. Barreling of the specimen was

caused by friction between the contact surfaces. It affected the stress of the syntactic foam under loading. At this strain, the formation of shear bands oriented at around 45° to the stress axis was the main deformation mode in the matrix. It is in this plane that the shear stress is maximum (Schmidt's Law). The second region of the flatwise compression curves in Figure 9a, is characterized by a relatively horizontal plateau. The horizontal plateau was attributed to the implosion of the microspheres, exposing their internal hollow feature under the increasing compression load. A densification process took place and was caused by a compaction process of the matrix polymer in the presence of voids induced by the crushing of microspheres. The inclined shear bands continued to propagate. The third region was characterized by a steep decrease in the load-displacement curve which was due to a failure. The portion of the curve labeled "fast crack propagation" is the point at which a crack propagated and greatly weakened the structural integrity of the material. In Figure 9a, a SEM micrograph of a fractured surface of a fragment separated from the sidewall is also presented. The presence of both crushed and uncrushed beads was observed. Some were removed from the matrix surface. It is evident that the hollow space exposed by the fracture of hollow spheres was due to the incapability of wall thickness of spheres to withstand the applied load. The images clearly show a gap between the microsphere and the matrix, which means a poor adhesion between the two phases. Indeed, fillers were not coated.

By comparison with a typical compression stress-strain of phenolic resole matrix (see Figure 9b), the compressive yield strength decreased with introducing hollow glass microspheres, especially as they were not coated. They acted as voids and weakened the structure.

Figure 9: Typical compression stress-strain curve of (a) phenolic resole syntactic foam with a SEM micrograph of a fractured surface and (b) phenolic resole matrix.

Damage mechanisms from tomography observation (qualitative)

Reconstructed 2D slices corresponding to each step (initial state and after compression to -27.5 and 30.75 MPa) are shown in Figure 10. The slices shown were extracted perpendicular to the compression axis. Observation of the initial state shows that the internal microstructure of the sample can be reasonably well analyzed at this resolution: the hollow glass spheres appear in white while the polymer matrix is grey. The third component (entrapped internal gas in the glass spheres) is black. Due to the high volume fraction of spheres, some of them are touching each other. The matrix has some pores of different size due to both the manufacturing process (air bubbles induced by mixing) but also to the initial presence of water as solvent in the phenolic resin. As curing occurs at room temperature in the present work, a significant proportion of this water is present as liquid contained within the pores and it evaporates with time. The presence of imperfect objects can be detected: a large majority of the spheres are hollow but there is also a small fraction of imperfect objects induced by the fabrication process of the spheres. After the step of compression ($\sigma = -27.5$ MPa), a large number of spheres are broken and fragmented in several pieces detached from the matrix. Although being indirect evidence, this indicates a weak adherence between hollow glass microspheres and phenolic matrix. During the following step of compression ($\sigma = -30.75$ MPa), more microspheres are observed to break. Some broken spheres disappear by filling empty cavities by the phenolic matrix. Cracks also appear along the broken microspheres.

Figure 10: Reconstructed 2D slices perpendicular to the load axis extracted from the 3D images of phenolic syntactic foam: (a) before compression; (b) after the first step of compression ($\sigma = -27.5$ MPa); (c) after the third step of compression ($\sigma = -30.75$ MPa).

9 CONCLUSIONS

A new in situ method allowing combined measurement of mechanical and thermal properties during cure was presented in this work. These measurements were carried out with the new thermal cell METRAVIB HFC200 installed on a METRAVIB DMA+450. The resin were contained into a mold where its base and cover included heat flux sensors. This allowed the monitoring of changes in temperature and thermal flux as well as stiffness and damping factor during cure. The curing process of phenolic resole resin was used in this work to demonstrate the capability of this new approach. The phenomena of gelation (gel time) and vitrification were study by investigating the effects of different factors (catalyst rate, volume, room cure temperature, introduction of hollow glass microspheres) on cure kinetic behaviour. The results were correlated with the sample temperature and heat flux data. They can act as inhibitors or accelerators with regard to the reacting system. There were a lot of physic-chemical parameters that had to be taken into account. The condensation cure reaction of phenolic resole resin at room temperature complicated even more to establish a kinetic model and a time-temperature-transformation diagram. Indeed, phenolic resole systems with cold cure are ‘living’ materials with increasing temperature, with the combination of two phenomena: vaporization of water and other volatiles, and post-curing.

The compression behaviour of syntactic polymer foams reinforced with hollow glass spheres has been studied during uniaxial compression experiments, both with a macroscopic test and coupled with high-resolution X-ray tomography observation using synchrotron radiation. It was shown that the damage was located in shear bands, and a better understanding of the damage mechanism at the scale of fillers was allowed: how the hollow glass microspheres were affected, how the three-phase microstructure changed.

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